

Effect of Protein on Soil Erosion by Water

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The effect of protein (gelatine) on eroded and uneroded soils (0-20 cms. depth) collected from semi-desert (Agra); Arid (Allahabad), semi-arid (Saharanpur), sub-humid (Gorakhpur); Vindhyan (Mirzapur) and Bundelkhand (Jhansi) regions of the State of Uttar Pradesh (India) was observed. These soils were treated with 1% and 2% gelatine and kept for 15 days and 30 days for reaction in aqueous media. Generally, the eroded soils have lower erosion coefficients with 1% gelatine than those of uneroded soils. Greater period of contact between the gelatine and soils (here 30 days) with both the concentration recorded lower erosion coefficients (better check of soil erosion) except those of Vindhayan and sub-humid regions.

THE efficiency of an organic matter to check soil erosion will greatly depend upon its chemical composition¹. A proteinaceous organic matter will behave differently as compared to an organic matter rich in either carbohydrates or fats and oils. Since, the protein is an important constituent of plant residues and different organic substances are commonly employed for replenishing soil fertility and improving soil condition, it would be worthwhile to see its role on soil erosion. In the present investigation, attempt has therefore been made to determine if protein has any effect on erosion behaviour of the soils.

Experimental

Eroded and uneroded soil samples from 0-20 cms. depth were collected from semi-desert (Agra), arid (Allahabad), semi-arid (Saharanpur), sub-humid (Gorakhpur), Vindhyan (Mirzapur) and Bundelkhand (Jhansi) regions of the State of Uttar Pradesh (India). Lang's² factor was used for the classification of soils to the above mentioned soil-climatic regions.

These soils were air-dried, pulverised in an agate-mortar and passed through 100-mesh (British Standard) sieve. Physico-chemical properties of soils were done (Table 1) by the reported methods³

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION AND SOME OTHER PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

Properties	Agra (semi-desert)		Allahabad (arid)		Saharanpur (semi-arid)		Gorakhpur (sub-humid)		Mirzapur (Vindhyan)		Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	
	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded	Un-eroded	Eroded
Texture	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy loam	Sandy clay loam	Loam	Clay loam	Clay
Cation exchange capacity (m.e./100 g. soil)	9.95	9.45	12.80	11.60	8.25	14.10	10.65	11.25	10.50	13.80	26.00	28.65
Silica p. c.	89.85	87.65	87.95	85.15	90.95	87.45	89.15	88.05	84.45	81.25	73.95	72.85
Sesquioxide p. c.	5.75	6.50	7.35	8.50	4.00	6.55	5.15	5.90	8.85	10.75	13.50	13.75
Calcium p. c. (CaO)	0.16	0.23	0.34	0.41	0.14	0.25	0.17	0.21	0.23	0.25	0.93	0.94
Calcium + Magnesium p. c.	1.41	1.58	1.14	1.36	0.64	1.00	0.67	0.71	0.88	1.00	2.98	3.09
Total organic carbon p. c.	0.14	0.11	0.27	0.20	0.20	0.15	0.35	0.26	0.41	0.35	0.36	0.32
pH	7.70	7.30	7.30	7.20	7.50	7.50	7.10	7.60	6.70	7.00	9.00	9.10

Erosion of natural and protein (gelatine) treated soils was determined by De-Subhash Erosion Apparatus. In this apparatus the soil at its water-holding capacity is allowed to erode by water, dropped artificially, and the amount of soil thus eroded on different set of conditions viz. slope, time, intensity of run-off etc. is collected and measured. The erosion coefficients were then calculated from the equation :

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{X-x}{X}$$

where,

- k=erosion coefficient
- t=time interval
- X=the initial effective mass of the soil
- x=the quantity of soil eroded.

For protein treatment, the soils were added with 1% and 2% gelatine (1% gelatine mixed with distilled water) and kept for 15 and 30 days time after bringing the initial moisture status of the soil to its water holding capacity level. Reduction of erosion coefficient is taken to be equal to the erosion coefficient of soil without the treatment of protein minus the erosion coefficients of soil with the treatment of protein

Results and Discussion

The extent of reduction in erosion coefficients (erosion coefficient of natural soil – erosion coefficient of treated soil) for the soils treated with gelatine and subjected to erosion on different slope percentages have been given in Tables 2 to 5.

TABLE 2—REDUCTION OF EROSION COEFFICIENT OF THE SOILS TREATED WITH GELATINE (1% GELATINE, KEPT FOR 15 DAYS)

Soils		Slope			
Place	Nature	1%	2%	4%	8%
Agra (Semi-desert)	Un-eroded	- 0.35	10.77	-20.66	- 20.25
	Eroded	-13.54	-10.80	- 3.88	- 30.99
Allahabad (Arid)	Un-eroded	- 2.28	-11.26	-10.43	-109.93
	Eroded	9.54	17.68	31.99	27.70
Saharanpur (Semi-arid)	Un-eroded	- 4.53	- 5.11	0.13	16.55
	Eroded	- 0.18	2.08	20.80	25.08
Gorakhpur (Sub-humid)	Un-eroded	- 6.88	4.92	13.67	14.19
	Eroded	-25.19	-11.83	-25.46	-112.52
Mirzapur (Vindhyan)	Un-eroded	-10.04	-10.51	-10.63	- 11.33
	Eroded	- 8.61	-12.38	- 7.28	- 4.04
Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	Un-eroded	0.70	2.92	3.30	4.25
	Eroded	4.81	4.18	6.94	10.77

TABLE 3—REDUCTION OF EROSION COEFFICIENT OF THE SOILS TREATED WITH GELATINE (2% GELATINE, KEPT FOR 15 DAYS)

Soils		Slope			
Place	Nature	1%	2%	4%	8%
Agra (Semi-desert)	Un-eroded	2.49	12.32	-25.64	12.30
	Eroded	- 1.02	5.43	20.20	- 26.84
Allahabad (Arid)	Un-eroded	- 3.79	-10.89	-15.70	- 36.42
	Eroded	7.55	22.13	44.30	45.45
Saharanpur (Semi-arid)	Un-eroded	- 1.72	- 2.45	0.51	20.74
	Eroded	- 8.60	- 8.41	5.43	- 0.64
Gorakhpur (Sub-humid)	Un-eroded	- 6.22	1.41	19.98	11.56
	Eroded	-47.27	-48.39	-52.87	-157.38
Mirzapur (Vindhyan)	Un-eroded	-20.89	-30.80	-28.56	- 40.08
	Eroded	- 0.29	0.42	1.75	4.20
Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	Un-eroded	1.42	4.10	5.00	7.11
	Eroded	5.47	4.87	7.85	10.98

TABLE 4—REDUCTION OF EROSION COEFFICIENT OF THE SOILS TREATED WITH GELATINE (1% GELATINE, KEPT FOR 30 DAYS)

Soils		Slope			
Place	Nature	1%	2%	4%	8%
Agra (Semi-desert)	Un-eroded	-0.53	13.27	36.86	21.46
	Eroded	1.08	7.12	4.15	-77.28
Allahabad (Arid)	Un-eroded	2.94	-6.70	4.66	-68.63
	Eroded	7.72	13.90	25.45	38.68
Saharanpur (Semi-arid)	Un-eroded	1.64	0.77	16.43	2.07
	Eroded	1.97	2.05	17.12	19.56
Gorakhpur (Sub-humid)	Un-eroded	-9.24	9.29	21.63	39.63
	Eroded	3.58	8.70	-3.58	-26.45
Mirzapur (Vindhyan)	Un-eroded	-1.42	-6.45	-3.82	-12.11
	Eroded	7.39	9.43	12.76	16.08
Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	Un-eroded	2.44	5.83	4.42	5.99
	Eroded	4.09	4.90	9.19	12.95

TABLE 5—REDUCTION OF EROSION COEFFICIENT OF THE SOILS TREATED WITH GELATINE (2% GELATINE, KEPT FOR 30 DAYS)

Place	Soils	Nature	Slope			
			1%	.2%	4%	8%
Agra (Semi-desert)	Un-eroded		5.99	-1.01	32.04	51.28
	Eroded		7.27	14.23	28.79	36.68
Allahabad (Arid)	Un-eroded		0.44	3.10	4.61	1.49
	Eroded		6.93	29.76	44.81	101.37
Saharanpur (Semi-arid)	Un-eroded		0.40	-1.66	16.62	18.72
	Eroded		0.98	0.19	9.70	7.43
Gorakhpur (Sub-humid)	Un-eroded		-3.51	9.75	19.37	52.48
	Eroded		4.99	9.13	-10.77	-6.19
Mirzapur (Vindhyan)	Un-eroded		-6.11	-24.07	-22.66	-20.45
	Eroded		8.19	10.78	15.16	1.52
Jhansi (Bundelkhand)	Un-eroded		2.18	4.65	4.63	7.10
	Eroded		4.19	5.54	9.44	11.49

It is interesting to note that reduction of erosion coefficients depend upon such factors as soil-climatic regions, concentration of gelatine, the period for which it has been allowed to react with the soil, and also the eroded and uneroded nature of the soil of a particular region. The eroded soils generally appear to have lower erosion coefficients in presence of gelatine than the uneroded ones, and this is particularly true with 1% treatment. The soils treated with 1% and 2% gelatine and kept for 15 days show some check in the soils of Bundelkhand and arid regions but in the soils of other regions the erosion has virtually increased. In case of 30 days treatment with both the concentration, almost all the soils record lower erosion coefficients except those of Vindhyan and sub-humid regions. In general, better check is obtained according to the following order :

2%, 30 days > 1%, 30 days > 1%, 15 days > 2%, 15 days.

However, it cannot be avoided mentioning that the check of soil erosion in presence of protein is not very encouraging. Some check can only be expected when gelatine is allowed to react with the soil for about 30 days, specially with 2% concentration, before the onset of monsoon or any artificial irrigation. From these observations it appear that the time given for forming clay-protein complexes, depending upon the physico-chemical conditions of the soils, is important for greater check of soil erosion in presence of this chemical substance. In the absence of any detail work about the relation of soil erosion check in presence of protein and its decomposition under different soil conditions, it cannot be said definitely which of soil chemical factor contributed more to the check of soil erosion.

The lower check of soil erosion in presence of proteins appears to be due to its amphoteric nature. When protein is added to the soil the negative part of the protein molecule is repulsed and its positive part is attracted towards the negative part of the soil particles. Such orientation of the protein molecules result in an increase in the negativity of the soil particles and as a result of which the soil particles repulse each other thus

decreasing the bonds between the particles and increasing their easy susceptibility to the onslaught of water molecules. In other words, a protein-treated soil get easily suspended in water and the particles are easily carried away depending upon the slope percentage of the soil. This situation is more accentuated on the surface because the positive part of the water dipole pulls the negative part of the protein molecule and this in turn removes the soil particle. With more time the bond between the positive part of the protein and the negative part of the soil particles become stronger and then it becomes difficult for the positive part of the water dipole to remove the soil particles from the main body of the soil.

The check will also be more in a similar fashion for the soils which are cation-saturated in which case some positive charges are left on the surface. Under such conditions, amphoteric protein molecule gets strongly bonded with its negative part oriented towards the soil surface followed by the negative part of the water dipole oriented on the positive part on such a protein-soil complex. Under such conditions, the gravitational force as a result of slope effect cannot easily pull out the water dipole and the water dipole in their turn the protein-soil-particle complex. This appears to be the explanation for greater check of erosion of the soils treated with protein and kept for about 30 days in comparison to those kept for 15 days.

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